

MSc Architectural Lighting Design

Master Thesis Booklet

2024-2025

Welcome to the Lighting Family!

The Lighting Design division congratulates the spring 2025 graduates at KTH School of Architecture in the Architectural Lighting Design Master! The individual thesis project, 15 ECTS, concludes the one-year programme in Architectural Lighting Design, 60 ECTS.

Throughout this “year of light”, the students first answer questions formulated by teachers and supervisors. Before the start of the Thesis, the students should have learnt to answer these questions, as well as to motivate their answers and their design choices in situations that are progressively more complex. The thesis marks a new step in the learning process; the students formulate their own questions and answer them using the most appropriate and feasible methods, supported by their tutors and teachers. In the age of continuous technological development of light sources, controls and AI, and of deep societal transformation, the ability to create and solve questions is becoming increasingly important. The students’ group represented in this booklet developed self-formulated research questions in the lighting design field that touch a multitude of topics.

Most theses included an investigatory approach into the design process, either in the question formulation, the literature search, the experimental testing or in the design of the conceptual proposals. In some case in all of these phases. This suggests the students’ need to integrate an evidence-based approach into the designers’ toolkit, which might be explained by their ambition to find evidence of their choices. Even most important, after the “year of light” education, their toolkit is filled with care and attention to users, spaces, the environment and societal needs. In fact, social and environmental sustainability are at the core of the activities of the Lighting Design division and of KTH. Each thesis needed to address at least one of the 17 goals promoted by the United Nations

in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>). The goals addressed by the students are listed here:

The Lighting Design division would like to acknowledge all the tutors who offered their knowledge, experience and time to support the ALD students. And we would like to acknowledge the external critics (ALD alumni Isabel Villar and Yousef Tavakoli) who enriched the discussion during the final presentation days. And finally, the Center of Academic Writing at KTH for the excellent support.

To all graduate students: welcome to the lighting design community and to the “lighting family”! Your ingenuity and dedication show great vitality and creativity, and a promise of hope for the future.

The Lighting Design division

Federico Favero (Course Responsible) ffavero@kth.se
Ute Besenecker (Course Examiner)
Stavroula Angelaki (Teacher)
Hamidreza Eizadi (Teacher, Lab responsible)
Foteini Kyriakidou (Teacher, acting Programme Director)
Rodrigo Muro (Programme Director)
Gerhard Rehm (Teacher)

Index and thematic clusters

The presentations were grouped in 6 thematic clusters, see below, which enabled discussion of individual and group considerations.

Integrative/Artificial lighting

Scarlette Torrealba Valladares
Filippa Pantelaiou
Beatrice Bartels

Biophilic Lighting

Cynthia Saadeh
Ian Bezemer
Elizabeth Watson

Hospitality and Food Lighting

Sasha Jimenez
Ember Peters
Dario Irawan

Visual Stimuli in the Lab and in the Field

Harshit Poddar
Sofia Stefanopoulou
Sara Jalil Dokhti Mamaghani

Affordance, Control and Inclusion

Lucia Sancho Garcia
Veronica Isabel Lopez Acosta
Sana Faheema Razeek

Integrative/Daylighting

Min Li
Minjee Kim
Mahbuba Sultana
Ei Khine Pwint Phyu

Integrative/Artificial Lighting

Scarlette Torrealba Valladares

Filippa Pantelaiou

Beatrice Bartels

Waiting to See: Lighting analysis and recommendations for Emergency Waiting Area at St.Eriks Ögonsjukhuset

Author: Scarlett Torrealba Valladares

Tutor: Per Nylén

Figure 1: Waiting area St. Erik Eye Hospital

Abstract:

Human vision is crucial for interacting with the environment. When vision is compromised, lighting design becomes critical, as inadequate lighting conditions can exacerbate discomfort and disability. Standard hospital lighting often fails to meet the diverse needs of patients, particularly those experiencing ophthalmic emergencies involving pain, anxiety, and photosensitivity. This study examines the lighting conditions in the ophthalmic emergencies waiting area at St Erik Eye Hospital.

Current lighting conditions were analysed through on-site measurements and a staff questionnaire. The findings revealed an intention to reduce light levels to address the needs of photosensitive patients. However, issues with glare from reflective surfaces and low contrast in key areas were also identified. The staff questionnaire also showed that medical staff are aware that patients experience discomfort due to the lighting conditions. This highlights the need for more adequate lighting. Ophthalmic conditions were categorised based on lighting needs: Group P for photophobia and glare sensitivity and Group C for low vision and contrast sensitivity. Lighting recommendations were developed for specific visual impairments. The findings emphasise the necessity of patient-centred lighting design to enhance well-being.

Keywords: Lighting Design for Healthcare, Lighting for Visual Impairments, St. Erik Eye Hospital

Figure 2: Steps with low contrast

Figure 3: Steps with high contrast

Glare in Realistic Workplace Environments: A Comparative Analysis of UGR values

Author: Filippa Pantelaiou

Tutors: Jan Wienold, Dond Hyun Kim

Abstract:

Discomfort glare has a negative impact on humans' well-being, particularly in workplaces where stress, and sensory overstimulation are common. By prioritising the users, we try to create glare-free environments, relying on manufacturer's data, or the outputs of the various simulation programs. Therefore the need to verify the validity of these methods is essential. The thesis investigates glare, caused by artificial lighting, in two field studies (four rooms in total) and compares two UGR evaluation methods: through Relux, a light simulation software and through HDR imaging processed through evalglare in Radiance. The illuminance levels are also evaluated. The values differ significantly, which shows that simulations might not depict real life situations, of which the dynamic and the complexity affect glare. This highlights the need for further development on approaches that combine technological knowledge in real-time settings. The thesis also tries to increase awareness on the situation and motivate the professionals to assess glare from different perspectives for a trustworthy result.

Keywords: discomfort glare, HDR measurements, simulation software, evalglare, Radiance

Figure 1: Room and Observer setting for UGR assessment

Figure 2: HDR fisheye images

Figure 3: Relux perspectives and UGR table

Light, Sleep, and Cognition: Evaluating Dynamic Lighting in Academic Settings

Author: Beatrice Akiko Bartels

Tutor: Arne Lowden

Figure 1: Library room group 15 3D view

Abstract:

This experimental study investigates the effects of dynamic lighting (DL) with a cloud function on cognitive performance, subjective sleepiness, mental effort, and lighting appraisal in partially sleep-deprived university students. Sixteen participants, all international students, were exposed to two lighting conditions: dynamic lighting and static lighting. The experiment was conducted in a controlled academic setting: a library windowless study room. While no statistically significant differences were found in objective performance measures, subjective appraisals indicated a more positive perception of the environment under DL. Although limited by a small sample size and short exposure duration, the findings suggest that dynamic lighting could contribute to psychological comfort for partially sleep-deprived students in educational settings and point to the need for future research on a larger scale with extended exposure periods.

Keywords: Dynamic lighting - Sleep deprivation - Cognitive performance - Comfort - Education

Figure 2: testing day with a participant

Figure 3: testing setting, view from the entrance

Biophilic Lighting

Cynthia Saadeh

Ian Bezemer

Elizabeth Watson

Beyond Windows

Author: Cynthia Saadeh

Tutor: Elena Mokeeva Hansson

Figure 1: The Doctrine of Flux and the Unity of Opposites - *JONATHAN BOUSQUET*

Abstract:

Lighting has a profound impact on our well-being and productivity, often in ways we don't fully realize. In many offices, the lighting is harsh and overly intense, creating discomfort and glare that can affect both physical health and mental clarity. This thesis explores the potential of biophilic lighting design to improve the working environment, specifically in windowless spaces. Through a case study of an office in Cepheid, Sweden housed in a warehouse mezzanine with no access to natural light or outdoor views. I examine how nature-inspired lighting solutions can counteract the negative effects of traditional, high-intensity artificial lighting. The research investigates how lighting influences mood, productivity, and our perception of time, and highlights how the lack of natural light in windowless spaces leads to feelings of isolation and fatigue. By integrating biophilic design strategies, such as adjustable light intensity and color temperature, along with dynamic lighting effects that mimic natural patterns, this thesis proposes a shift toward lighting solutions that enhance both comfort and well-being. The findings support the idea that thoughtful, nature-inspired lighting can foster a healthier, more engaging workspace while also aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 3: Good Health and Well-Being. The goal is to create work environments that are not only better for people but also more sustainable in the long run.

Keywords: lighting design, biophilic design, office lighting, well-being, productivity, sustainable lighting, visual ergonomics.

Figure 2: UMSU - Mental Health

Figure 3: Shutterstock

Entities of Light: Reimagining Dynamics In Architectural Lighting with Qualities of Bioluminescence

Author: Ian Nathan Bezemer

Tutor: Federico Favero

Figure 1: Prototype in action, sideview

Abstract:

While bioluminescence is a well-studied phenomenon that currently has many uses in biotechnology, potential applications within architectural contexts are still novel and conceptual. Currently, bioluminescent lighting is unlikely to be a replacement for LEDs; despite benefits in terms of sustainability, bioluminescent light is simply too dim, temporal and maintenance-heavy. For architectural bioluminescence to be viable, a new perspective is needed on what architectural lighting could be. In this paper, I explored a conceptual paradigm for architectural lighting that is more dynamic and life-like, by integrating qualities of bioluminescence. Through experimentation and research, qualities of interaction with bioluminescent algae (*Pyrocystis Lunula*) were assessed, which were then used as inspiration for an interactive LED lighting prototype. This prototype revealed that bioluminescence-inspired lighting - with fluid and natural interaction - could turn lighting into a magical and dynamic experience. Seamless integration with architecture could transform spaces into playful interactive canvases. I then argue that integration of actual bioluminescent organisms might be possible, although further development is needed to ensure a higher luminous intensity and a sustainable human-non-human relationship. Since bioluminescence is unlikely to reach demands for task-related lighting, proposed applications are limited to temporary and intermediary spaces such as walkways and public recreational areas.

Keywords: Biophilic Design, Interaction Design, Biomimicry, Interactive Architecture, Post-human Design

Figure 2: Top-down view

Figure 3: Potential application in hallway

Exploring Mycelium-Based Composites for Sustainable Luminaire Design: With Focus on Light Characteristics

Author: Elizabeth Watson

Tutors: A. Jiménez Quero & A. Capezza

Figure 1: Mycelium Hyphae from an MBC 2,500 × magnification. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). Image: Antonio Capezza.

Abstract:

Mycelium-Based Composites (MBCs) offer a sustainable alternative to conventional materials in luminaire design. This study explores how the MBC surface interacts with light. Findings show that MBC surfaces provide high colour rendering and luminance but exhibit low reflectivity. Light characteristics differ between MBC surfaces grown against a form and those grown unconstrained, due to variations in hyphal orientation. When grown against a form, the hyphae align laterally, creating flatter surfaces with greater reflectivity but lower luminance. In contrast, the unconstrained surface develops more three-dimensional networks that scatter light more effectively, resulting in higher luminance and a brighter appearance. MBC surfaces absorb violet light around 420 nm, indicating potential to also filter harmful ultraviolet (UV) wavelengths, which could have significant applications in the lighting industry. As architectural design increasingly embraces sustainability, there's also a notable shift towards prioritizing luminance over general illumination, making MBCs a compelling option for future-oriented, environmentally conscious solutions. As a proof of concept, 'Crack' luminaire was developed—a simple, scalable design that juxtaposes a rigid block form with the chaotic, luminous interior revealed through a rupture.

Keywords: mycelium, luminaire, light qualities, mycelial hyphae

Figure 2: Light reflected off Aluminium, White and MBC, note MBC absorbs

Figure 3: Detail from the MBC luminaire 'Crack', inspired by Leonard Cohen's

Hospitality and Food Lighting

Sasha Jimenez

Ember Peters

Dario Irawan

Lighting for Immersiveness in Hospitality Interiors

Author: Sasha Jimenez

Tutor: Wenyi Kong

Figure 1: Rendering of lobby and restaurant connection with colors, materials, textures and lighting

Abstract:

Proposing a sustainable lighting design approach for hospitality interiors, building upon a previous adaptive reuse project in Astoria, Oregon. The core research investigates: *How do different lighting principles impact visual perception (such as how it enhances or distorts the appearance of materials, textures, and colors) ultimately influencing the sensory experiences of guests and their immersiveness in the space?*

Through a comparative analysis of three hotel case studies, utilizing the “7 factors of lighting” framework, the research examines how lighting influences atmosphere, material appearance, and the integration of functional and aesthetic qualities. The findings inform a comprehensive lighting design proposal for key hotel zones: a speakeasy, a combined lobby, restaurant, and mezzanine bar, and a guest suite, aiming to create unique, immersive guest experiences while adhering to sustainable design principles.

Keywords: Adaptive Reuse, Visual Perception, Material Interaction

Figure 2: Rendering of mezzanine level bar

Figure 3: Rendering of Speakeasy

Integrative Lighting in a Windowless Food Court

Author: Ember Peters

Tutor: Yvonne de Kort

Figure 1: Section conceptual lighting design food court

Abstract:

Daylight has an important impact on our biological clocks (Peeters et al., 2020). We spend a lot of our time indoors, which can interrupt our light-dark cycle (Schlangen, 2022). Not enough daylight can lead to various health issues, which are a non-image forming effect of light (Schöllhorn et al., 2023). To measure how much a light source affects the circadian rhythm we measure the m-EDI. A recommended m-EDI is 250 lux at the eye (Brown et al., 2022). In shopping malls windows are often intentionally left out windows to interfere with the visitors' sense of time (Modi, 2024). In the Kista Gallerian Food court there is also a big space that has no daylight at all, which can influence the circadian rhythm of the employees and the visitors. That is why this food court is the site for this research. A case study, a site analysis and an experiment will be used to create a conceptual proposal for a new lighting plan at this site. The case study is the shopping mall Hoog Catharijne in Utrecht which uses integrative lighting, the site analysis will be an analysis of the use and existing lighting of the food court and the experiment will show that the ideal CCT for the pendant lighting in the food court will be 3500K in combination with a m-EDI of 250lux.

With this research we hope to answer the following research question; *'How can integrative lighting be optimised in shopping malls to enhance workers' and visitors' sense of time and support their biological rhythms, yet at the same time provide a pleasant atmosphere and positive food experience, considering the balance between correlated colour temperature (CCT), intensity and the melanopic equivalent daylight index (m-EDI)?'*

Keywords; Circadian rhythm, Windowless, Food court, Integrative lighting, CCT

Figure 2: Lighting scenarios experiment

Figure 3: Boxplot of how the colour of the food is perceived by the participants

Refining Ambiance: Light Distribution Strategies to Elevate Food Appearance

Author: Dario Irawan

Tutor: Ryan Salim

Figure 1: Food appearance under wide beam spotlight without ambient lighting

Abstract:

Dining table task lighting plays a key role in enhancing the appearance of food. When combined with ambient lighting and high-quality food, it becomes part of the recipe of success in the food industry. This research focuses on light distribution on the dining table and its surrounding space, aiming to identify ideal task lighting conditions that not only enhance the visual appeal of food but also contribute to the overall fine-dining experience. The study includes case analyses of several restaurants around Stockholm to observe diverse lighting conditions, as well as an experiment involving 30 respondents. Participants evaluated four lighting scenarios, developed based on the case studies, on aspects such as ambiance appreciation, menu readability, food appearance, the facial appearance of the person seated opposite, and overall atmosphere. The results show that the presence of ambient lighting is essential for balancing light distribution, creating aesthetically pleasing compositions, and establishing a sense of place. However, ambient lighting must be carefully adjusted to maintain focus on food presentation while ensuring good menu readability and flattering facial appearance. When thoughtfully combined with other sensory elements, lighting can help effectively create the desired dining atmosphere.

Keywords: Light Distribution, Task Lighting, Food Appearance, Restaurant Ambiance

Figure 2: View of the constructed mock-up dining room with task and ambient lighting

Figure 3: On-going experiment

Visual Stimuli in the Lab and in the Field

Harshit Poddar

Sofia Stefanopoulou

Sara Jalil Dokhti Mamaghani

Light and Texture: Influence of Artificial Lighting on the Visual Perception of Real Physical Textures

Author: Harshit Poddar

Tutor: Gerhard Rehm

Figure 1: Experimental Lab station

Abstract:

Textures play a vital role in how materials and surfaces are perceived, shaping both functional understanding and aesthetic experience within architectural and spatial contexts. While texture perception is often discussed in relation to touch or materiality, its visual interpretation under directional lighting conditions remains underexplored. This study investigates how the angle of incidence and the relative distance of ceiling-mounted artificial lighting influence the visual perception of real physical textures. The research focuses on three surface types—matte, glossy, and pitted—examined under four lighting angles (90°, 60°, 45°, 30°). Eighteen participants rated the textures using semantic differential scales covering a range of objective and subjective perceptual attributes. Findings indicate that steeper angles (e.g., 90°) enhance texture legibility through stronger surface relief and sharper contrast, while shallower angles (e.g., 30°) reduce visual clarity but increase perceived softness and comfort. These results highlight how variations in lighting direction shape the balance between perceived material definition and visual comfort, suggesting an interdependent relationship between surface readability and affective evaluation. The research offers insights for applications in lighting design, perceptual studies, and spatial planning where surface texture plays a key role in shaping user experience.

Keywords: Artificial lighting, physical textures, visual perception, contrast, semantics

Figure 2: Matte texture

Figure 3: Pitted texture

Figure 4: Glossy texture

Lighting and Spatial Perception: Exploring Depth and Affordances in Public Interiors

Author: Sofia Stefanopoulou

Tutor: Foteini Kyriakidou

Figure 1: Composite diagram by the author showing all luminance comparisons across the nine predefined regions.

Abstract:

This thesis explores how lighting layers influence spatial depth perception and support affordances in public interior environments. Using the KTH Library Hall in Stockholm as a case study, the study combines luminance mapping across nine predefined image regions with a perception-based questionnaire to examine the relationship between lighting distribution, spatial legibility, and user experience. The findings indicate that luminance variation significantly shapes spatial comprehension, particularly along peripheral and vertical axes. Contrasts in brightness appear to contribute to the perception of volume and directionality, while subtle transitions between light zones indicate different spatial functions, such as movement, pause, or focus. Responses from the questionnaire reinforce the idea that lighting cues are instrumental in how users interpret and navigate space. This research contributes to a broader understanding of lighting as a visual and cognitive tool in architectural design. By integrating perceptual strategies with technical metrics, this study introduces layered lighting as an approach to enhance comfort, orientation, and inclusivity in public interiors, thereby supporting Sustainable Development Goals 3.4 and 11.7.

Keywords: depth, layered lighting, light zones, affordances.

Figure 2: Sketches representing perception zones shaped by light's interaction with architectural form over time illustrate how changing daylight conditions influence perceived depth.

Lighting Design in Fashion Retail: Fast Fashion vs. Luxury (2014–2024)

Author: Sara Jalildokhti Mamaghani

Tutor: Thomas Schielke

Figure 1. Gucci 2014–2024 (top row) and Zara 2014–2024 (bottom row) 3D models and rendered visuals based on photographic references.

Abstract:

This thesis explores how lighting design functions as a strategic tool in fashion retail by comparing fast fashion and luxury environments. It focuses on four global brands—Zara and H&M (fast fashion) versus Gucci and Prada (luxury)—and analyzes lighting strategies from 2014 to 2024 through visual case studies, academic literature, and a perception-based survey. The visual analysis is based on 3D models and renders created by the author, reconstructed from real store photographs to illustrate lighting atmospheres across two timeframes. As retail design becomes increasingly experience-driven, lighting plays a central role in shaping customer perception, emotional response, and brand identity. Luxury brands tend to use layered, scenographic lighting to communicate exclusivity and depth, while fast fashion retailers favor more functional and dynamic lighting schemes to enhance accessibility and efficiency. The study applies Richard Kelly’s framework—ambient luminescence, focal glow, and play of brilliants—to examine how different lighting approaches support storytelling and spatial communication. By comparing the evolving use of lighting across brand tiers, the research highlights lighting’s ability to reinforce brand narratives and influence experiential engagement. Ultimately, the findings position lighting as a powerful medium for design expression and strategic retail communication.

Keywords:

Retail lighting, Lighting strategy, Lighting perception, Lighting design,

Figure 2: Prada 2014 interior render.

Figure 3: Prada 2024 interior render.

Affordance, Control and Inclusion

Lucia Sancho Garcia

Veronica Isabel Lopez Acosta

Sana Faheema Razeek

Circadian Lighting at Home: A Comparative Study of Control Protocols

Author: Lucia Sancho Garcia

Tutor: Ken Appleman

Figure 1: Protocols Analysed for a Circadian Smart Home

Abstract:

Integrating circadian principles into residential lighting design can potentially enhance health, well-being, and daily performance. This thesis investigates how lighting control protocols support personalised, adaptive circadian lighting in smart home environments. Through a comparative analysis of four protocols—DALI, KNX, Zigbee, and Matter—the study evaluates each system’s capabilities in scene scheduling, sensor integration, multi-zone management, user personalisation, interoperability, and ease of installation. A qualitative matrix and three scenario-based case studies assess protocol performance in context. Results show that while DALI and KNX offer superior technical precision, their complexity and professional installation requirements limit their applicability in everyday homes. In contrast, Zigbee and Matter provide greater flexibility, accessibility, and user-friendly control, making them better suited to dynamic residential needs. The study concludes with practical guidance for designers and users aiming to implement circadian lighting at home using technically capable and feasible protocols.

Keywords: Circadian Lighting, Smart Home, Lighting Control Protocols, Adaptive Systems

Figure 2: Criteria Evaluated

Interactive Design levels of Social inclusion: Case Studies of Interactive Urban Lighting in Sweden

Author: Veronica I. Lopez Acosta

Tutor: Federico Favero

Figure 1: cases studies selected to studies dynamic, adaptive, and interactive urban lighting.

Abstract:

This thesis investigates how the urban lighting system can support social interaction and promote inclusion in public gathering spaces. Traditional sustainable urban lighting has prioritized economic and technical standards for traffic safety and uniformity, often overlooking human experience and social engagement. The research addresses this gap by conducting a qualitative method study of three Swedish case studies involving interactive urban lighting and a social approach. Methods include site visits to assess observation of lighting quality and engagement by informal interviews with pedestrians and conversations with lighting designers responsible for those projects to understand how human-centered approaches were applied. The preliminary findings show that interactive urban lighting shows that the design of gathering spaces is more effective when community members are involved in the design process. Finally, the studio mentions the use of coloured lighting in lighting settings makes a difference in strengthening social cohesion. The work aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 11.3, and 3.4, supporting inclusive, sustainable urban design that also supports individual and collective well-being.

Keywords: interactive urban lighting, social inclusion, human-centered design, public gathering space.

Figure 2: Diagram illustrating the flow of interactive urban light in gathering areas. The system activates changing the condition of the environment.

Affordance of Lighting to Create Emotional Contrast in a Transportation Hub

Author: Sana Faheema Razeek

Tutor: Svante Pettersson

Figure 1: Photograph of working model

Abstract:

A location such as a transportation hub is one of the many architectural spaces where design is dictated through movement and efficiency rather than presence, pause and experience. The mechanical movement from one destination to the next has a deeper impact on mental wellbeing.

This thesis explores the affordances of lighting to create emotional contrast in such a transportation hub. It argues that transitional spaces –such as those found in transportation hubs- can hold character and emotional depth by using lighting as a tool.

Drawing on the theoretical frameworks of “affordances” and “affect,” the literature study examines the relationship between lighting and emotion. It is supported by case studies of spaces where light is used to evoke feeling and atmosphere. Findings from these studies were used to create a light and art installation over an escalator site at T-Centralen in Stockholm.

A working scaled model was built to conduct a brief user survey and understand emotional response. The results suggest that lighting does indeed have the affordances to create emotional contrast. Understanding this strong impact of lighting on emotion, the discussion emphasises the need for a sensitive and balanced approach to avoid overwhelming users.

Keywords: Emotional contrast, affordance, lighting, immersive experience, art

Figure 2: Reflections in design proposal

Figure 3: Photograph of working model

Integrative/Daylighting

Min Li

Minjee Kim

Mahbuba Sultana

Ei Khine Pwint Phyu

Framing Illumination: Toward a Resonant Window for Nordic Homes

Author: Min Li

Tutor: Foteini Kyriakidou and Gerhard Rehm

Figure 1: Daylight observation sketches in Nordic Homes

Abstract:

This thesis investigates how the lighting qualities of windows in Nordic homes have evolved over time, informed by cultural perceptions of light and dwelling. By analyzing three distinct domestic cases—a farmhouse in Skansen, the Aalto House, and a student accommodation at KTH—the study derives a design perspective that supports the development of a contemporary window prototype, integrating daylight and artificial light in response to Nordic living.

Through literature studies from anthropological and cultural perspectives, case studies, perceptual evaluation using the Perceived Indoor Lighting Quality (PILQ) method, light-zone(s) sketching, and physical modeling with daylighting simulations, the study explores how daylight access influence the temporal distribution of indoor light, as well as their impact on psychological comfort and mental well-being.

By focusing on human perception and lived experience, the project proposes a renewed architectural approach to housing openings—one that reframes the window as a vital interface between indoor life and the Nordic sky.

Keywords: Nordic windows, Daylighting, Integrated lighting, Domestic space, Vernacular contemporary design concept

Figure 2: The procedure of case study analysis

Right to Light: Daylight Simulation Research on Semi-Basement Housing (Banjiha) in South Korea

Author: Minjee Kim

Tutor: Majid Miri

Figure 1: Semi-Basement Housing Plan & Section

Abstract:

Semi-basement housing, known as “Banjiha,” highlights the challenges of housing inequality and urban poverty in South Korea. Originally built as bunkers, these spaces were later converted into housing due to rapid industrialization. They suffer from poor living conditions, including limited natural daylight, restricted views, and poor ventilation, all essential for health and well-being.

If daylight significantly influences quality of life, should semi-basement housing be considered acceptable for residential use? This research investigates daylight conditions in semi-basement housing through occupant interviews, on-site measurements, and 3D daylight simulations of three scenarios (Case Study 1). Comparing daylight levels with European standards shows that these housings fall significantly short of the minimum requirements for healthy living. Case Study 2 examines renovation strategies that improve daylight exposure by converting these spaces from residential to commercial use, showing notable but still insufficient improvements. Ultimately, this research aims to raise awareness of the health risks associated with semi-basement living and to propose design guidelines that could improve occupants’ health and well-being.

Keywords: Daylight, Window, Health, Well-being, Residence, Urban poverty

Figure 2: Case Study 1 (3 scenarios)

Figure 3: Case Study 2 (renovation)

Daylight Dynamics in Glazed Office Facades: A Case Study in Dhaka

Author: Mahbuba Sultana

Tutor: Stavroula Angelaki & Isabel Villar

Figure 1: Proposed facade shading configuration

Abstract:

Rapid urbanization in Dhaka has driven a surge in high-rise office buildings with fully glazed façades, reflecting a global architectural trend favoring transparency and daylight maximization. However, in Dhaka's hot and humid tropical climate, the extensive use of glass façades creates challenges such as visual discomfort, glare, and excessive brightness, which compromise occupant comfort and energy efficiency. This thesis investigates the impact of fully glazed office façades on daylight quality and visual comfort in Dhaka, focusing on daylight contrast and glare issues influenced by building orientation and climatic factors. Through a case study approach combining daylight simulation and on-site occupant surveys, the research evaluates current façade performance. In response, the thesis proposes optimized external shading solutions aimed at balancing daylight penetration with glare reduction to improve visual comfort and occupant well-being. Findings suggest that, without proper shading design, fully glazed façades may not deliver the expected sustainable benefits in Dhaka's context. The proposed façade shading modifications demonstrate significant improvements in reducing these issues while maintaining natural light penetration. This study highlights the importance of context-sensitive façade design in tropical climates to enhance both energy efficiency and indoor environmental quality.

Keywords: Building façade, Full glazed façade, tropical climate, daylight analysis, work environment, shading design

Figure 2: sDG - 44% for baseline scenario

Figure 3: sDG - 14% for proposed scenario

Daylight Optimization for Yangon Classrooms: Evaluation of Corridor Depth and Window Size

Author: Ei Khine Pwint Phyu

Tutor: Arlind Dervishaj

Figure 1: Elevation of the Simulation Model (with different window sizes)

Abstract:

The goal of this study is to investigate and evaluate the relationship of window size and corridor depth, and provide the best configurations for optimizing daylight performance of classrooms in tropical monsoon climate zone, with a focus on Yangon, Myanmar. Schools and universities from those regions often utilize exterior corridors as shaded transitional path between one room to another while offering daylight entry towards classrooms and reducing the possible glare it might occur. With parametric simulation approach, this paper explores how varying sill heights (0.6m, 0.8m, 1m, 1.25m, 1.5m), window sizes (height 2.1m, 1.9m, 1.7m, 1.45m, 1.2m and width 2m, 4m, 6m), and corridor depths (2m, 3m, 4m) affect daylight distribution and potential of glare across recommended façade orientations for tropical monsoon regions (South, South-east, South-west). Key daylight performance measuring metrics including spatial daylight autonomy (sDA), useful daylight illuminance (UDI), annual sunlight exposure (ASE), and spatial daylight glare probability (sDG) were utilized to perform evaluation process. Results imply that increasing window sizes, especially width, can enhance daylight availability but at the same time, can raise the potential of glare risk if the window sill height is not high enough and corridor depth is too shallow. Best result outcomes occur in classrooms with wide windows (especially 6m) at high window sill level (mostly 1.25m), and medium depth of corridors (mainly 3m). This study provides orientation specific recommendations with optimal window and corridor depth configurations. This thesis contributes to future daylight-responsive classroom design in tropical climates lacking formal daylight standards by addressing Sustainable Development Goals 3 (Good Health and Well-being) and 4 (Quality Education).

Keywords: Corridor Depth, Window Size, Daylight Performance, Metrics, Optimization

Figure 2: Intolerable Glare perceived in Classroom with 2m Corridor Depth

Figure 3: Imperceptible Glare perceived in Classroom with 4m Corridor Depth

The students in alphabetical order by surname:

Bartels, Beatrice

Bezemer, Ian

Irawan, Dario

Jalil Dokhti Mamaghani, Sara

Jimenez, Sasha

Kim, Minjee

Li, Min

Lopez Acosta, Veronica Isabel

Pantelaiou, Filippa

Peters, Ember

Poddar, Harshit

Pwint Phyu, Ei Khine

Razeek, Sana Faheema

Saadeh, Cynthia

Sancho Garcia, Lucia

Stefanopoulou, Sofia

Sultana, Mahbuba

Torrealba Valladares, Scarlett

Watson, Elizabeth

Instagram: Lighting Design Laboratory
LinkedIn: Lighting Design KTH

